

INVOLVING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION AND DIALOGUE IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185293>

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ABSTRACT

The function and location of conversation in instructional communication are the focus of this paper. The investigation highlights how crucial it is to properly structure discussion during educational communication, particularly when the material and learning process are oriented toward individual activities. The article's novelty lies in the fact that the author, being one of the first researchers to focus on such aspects of the dialogue in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, as the national-cultural specifics of speech behavior in the cultural environment, and the necessity of considering the fact that representatives of different nationalities have different requirements for his professional pedagogical approach and understand the teacher's behavior style differently.

Keywords: *pedagogical communication, dialogue, teaching Russian as a foreign language, personality-activity orientation, the learning process, speech behavior, the teacher's behavior style, pedagogical skill, language behavior, the personality of the teacher.*

It is well known that contemporary approaches to teaching Russian as a Foreign Language (RFL) prioritize the personal-activity orientation of both the process and the content. Since the teacher's capacity to facilitate productive, successful interactions with pupils frequently serves as the determining factor of his professionalism, it is only natural that the function and position of the teacher in this process are receiving an increasing amount of attention. Of course, the teacher's refusal of the authoritarian pedagogical paradigm and the practice of joint creativity between the teacher and the student will also further contribute to the fruitful dialogue “teacher-student”. Furthermore, when discussing pedagogical communication in its broadest sense, we must remember that it is both a tool and an objective of instruction. It also has a multicomponent structure, with the communicative act serving as the smallest structural unit. Numerous psychological, educational, and methodological works have examined issues of pedagogical communication, including those by I. A. Zimnyaya, A. A. Leontyev, A. V. Petrovsky,

and numerous others. Particularly well-known is V.V. Molchanovsky's "Teacher of Russian as a Foreign Language - Introduction to the Specialty," which provides a thorough account of the character and actions of the instructor. In this context, it is important to highlight that the predominant belief among many academics is that a modern RFL teacher should be an expert in the fields of language instruction and intercultural competency, rather than a language specialist. It seems that one of the most promising and productive forms of pedagogical interaction in the process of cognitive activity is educational dialogue, designed to ensure intersubjective communication with others as an equal subject. In addition to being multifunctional, educational dialogue fosters personal growth, guarantees collaboration and interaction during cognitive activities, aids in the organization and management of cognitive processes, serves as a tool for assessing the efficacy of cognitive activity, and is also a useful tool for reflection and process improvement. [Zimnyaya,2001]

Dialogic communication, which should be a required part of the educational process, is how concepts of interpersonal interaction are put into practice. The primary and most organic way to use language to accomplish the practical learning objective of being proficient in communication is through discourse. In this regard, it is challenging to overstate the function and significance of conversation in the framework of educational communication. Unfortunately, conversation is not frequently used as a methodological strategy in RFL instruction, despite the fact that it has the potential to help both teachers and students actively comprehend and critically analyze their own thought processes. However, it should be highlighted that the conduct itself, the dialogue's trajectory, is influenced by the laws of human communication as well as the speakers' unique worldview, and not just by the rules of language usage. As a result, the issue with the notion of "dialogue" affects not just linguistic fields but also other scientific fields. [Shumanskaya,2006]

According to the aforementioned, dialogic communication is one of the communication styles that embodies the subject-object form of interaction. It is founded primarily on the equality of partner positions and the value of accepting another person into one's inner world. The tenets of equality, cooperation, mutual understanding, and co-creation should also be the cornerstones of any strategy that emphasizes communication between the instructor and the students. With these methods, discourse can be a very effective way to pedagogically affect students and one of the mechanisms for helping them develop their personalities. As was previously mentioned, the course of a conversation is primarily determined by both linguistic norms and the canons of human communication. As a result, the standards for the educational conversational concepts that date back to Socrates' dialogues remain applicable today. The following are the most crucial for the instructor: the

teacher must have a clear understanding of his objectives before engaging in conversation; the teacher must pose difficulties to students while also suggesting solutions; Students must choose the right choice on their own and submit their choices as original ideas; the teacher should attempt to speak the interlocutor's language honestly and clearly, without favoring any one student over another; Selecting the appropriate interlocutor is also crucial, with a continuous emphasis on working together to find the best answer; remember that the capacity to focus attention is the first step in conducting a dialogue; never forget that the listener can only be persuaded and not left unconvinced by what is personally experienced and felt.

When planning communicative activities during a practical session on RFL, particularly planning a form like dialogue, there are also certain needs for the teacher's personality. We may spend a lot of time discussing what attributes a teacher should possess for this, but first it is important to identify the traits that would most likely cause him to struggle while setting up a discussion. The main causes of this are comfort, rigidity, and authoritarianism. You should start by getting rid of them. In order for a discussion to be successful, the instructor must view the student as an equal partner, a worthwhile individual who needs to be considered and assisted in realizing and developing all of his best human traits. Questions that the teacher wants answers to and that the students might find interesting might serve as the foundation for the conversation. It is important to be constantly tuned in to feedback, to encourage students to give it, to perceive any events and situations that arise during the dialogue as lessons for oneself, material for improvement.

And finally, the questions that the teacher poses should be of elementary interest to the students. One should keep in mind, among other things, the pedagogical process's unpredictable and uncontrollable aspects as well as the incompleteness of the student's developmental process. When developing dialogical interactions during the pedagogical communication process, all of the aforementioned points are unquestionably significant. Finally, it is also important to take into account the features of pedagogical communication in teaching RFL, the organization of which contains both universal and specific features. Persuasion, tact, the ability to organize foreign language communication and work in the classroom, a sufficient vocabulary, proficiency in speech technique and culture, its content, demandingness, and a sense of proportion in behavior are all examples of pedagogical communication skills. The realization of the communicative and educational function is intimately linked to the issue of pedagogical communication. It consists of instructional activities and specifies particular requirements for the teacher in terms of both foreign language proficiency and teaching methodologies. [Shipelevich,2000]

When learning a foreign language, a lot of thought should also be given to the student's motivations, which are connected to their surroundings and can influence their occurrence and development in either a favorable or negative way. Of course, the motivations for teaching a language are greatly influenced by the teacher's personality and the pedagogical communication he develops. Communication between teachers of different languages and cultures is one aspect of educational communication that requires consideration. This is crucial while teaching RFL, and the instructor must act from the perspective of the national-cultural distinctiveness of a native speaker's speech patterns, accounting for all the differences between the native and foreign languages and cultures. All of this is directly tied to the necessity of teaching a non-native language and its culture in order to guarantee the development of students' linguistic personalities, skills, and high degree of cognitive activity.

Students' individual psychological variations, which show out in many ways during language acquisition, also have an impact on the particular of educational communication in a foreign audience. The degree of professional attributes that an RFL instructor possesses, which are developed during professional pedagogical training, is undoubtedly a significant influence. Since an RFL teacher's pedagogical activity is defined by a certain communication style, a teacher cannot overlook the fact that pupils come from a different culture while arranging the content of educational activities. The particulars of the activity itself as well as the unique psychological traits of its participants are linked to the communication style selection various national community representatives have various expectations for a teacher's professional abilities based on how they view his behavior style. [Vasilyeva,1984]

To sum up, the teacher can overcome communication barriers during the educational process by taking into account the unique characteristics of the students' national mentality, the unique ways in which the pedagogical system operates, and the role that the teacher plays in this system. This will have an impact on how the students perceive and assimilate the knowledge they have learned, as well as how well they have adapted to the pedagogical process.

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